

Strengthening public engagement in AI-driven data research

Findings from a PEDRI and DARE UK Roundtable

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Executive Summary

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being used across data research domains to link, analyse and interpret large scale datasets for public benefit. While these developments offer significant opportunities, the training of AI models on sensitive data raises legitimate public concerns about security, bias, accountability and privacy. Building and maintaining public trust in AI in data research requires more than technical safeguards and regulation alone; it also depends on transparency, accountability and effective public involvement and engagement (PIE). In November 2025, the Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI) and DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) convened a sector-wide roundtable to share learnings and explore challenges, opportunities and priorities for strengthening PIE with AI in data research. This report summarises the key themes from those discussions and represents an initial step towards developing shared principles for effective PIE with AI and data research.

Key themes identified

The roundtable identified several key priorities for strengthening PIE with AI in data research, with ‘inclusion, equity and representation’ and ‘effective public deliberation’ emerging as the most significant.

Ensuring that underserved communities are actively involved and that public perspectives meaningfully inform the development and training of AI models was viewed as essential to trustworthy PIE practice across the sector. Alongside this, it was agreed that sustained, large-scale public deliberation is crucial for supporting informed decision-making and enabling people to explore the opportunities and risks of AI in data research in depth.

Building data and AI literacy across the wider public, including frontline public sector staff and policymakers, was also recognised as essential to support informed and constructive dialogue. Trust and transparency were seen to depend on clear communication about how data are used, where accountability sits, and the limitations of AI systems, alongside robust governance arrangements that integrate public perspectives through clear regulatory and quality assurance frameworks. It was further highlighted that there is a need for proactive efforts to counter sensational or misleading narratives through clear, evidence-based communication.

Finally, the use of high-quality, standardised data was regarded as foundational to trustworthy AI, and engagement activities should clearly convey its societal value through tangible, real-world examples.

Photos from the AI Roundtable held in York on 20 November 2025.

Next steps

PEDRI will coordinate sector-wide efforts on PIE with AI to share learning and avoid duplication. In 2026, DARE UK will lead, and seek to collaborate on, a UK-wide dialogue to better understand public views on the topic. By working together, the sector can avoid duplication, amplify impact and create a coherent approach that reflects public priorities.

Definitions

Term	Definition
Artificial intelligence (AI)	This term is often used to refer to a computer programme which takes in specific variables, queries a trained machine learning model and returns a result. It can also be used to mean the branch of science that develops new AI models or trains new AI models with new datasets to develop new AI products (UK TRE Glossary).
Data research	The process of collecting, analysing and interpreting data to help answer questions, identify patterns or support decision making. Data research can be carried out across various sectors from healthcare to business (PEDRI).
Machine learning	A subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) is a computer programming technique particularly suited to identifying patterns or rules in large amounts of data (UK TRE Glossary).
Public involvement and engagement (PIE)	Involvement and Engagement are interrelated. Involvement means that activities and research are carried out 'with' or 'by' members of the public, rather than 'to', 'about' or 'for' them (National Institute for Health and Care Research). Engagement describes the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of an organisation or research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit (National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement).
Sensitive data	Sensitive data is data which contains personally identifiable information such as names, addresses and identifying numbers. This data can still be sensitive once it has been de-identified (has had all personal identifiable information removed), particularly if there is potential for re-identification when used with other data. Commercial data such as retail information, business details or confidential product details may also be considered sensitive when used for research (DARE UK).
Trusted Research Environment (TRE)	A highly secure digital environment that provides access to sensitive data for analysis by approved researchers. A series of strict security measures protect the privacy of the people the data is about, significantly reducing the potential for data misuse or the possibility of re-identification of de-identified data. This enables researchers to securely analyse data as part of important projects to inform policy and practice and improve lives (DARE UK).

Introduction

The [Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative \(PEDRI\)](#) is a sector-wide partnership that brings together organisations working with data and statistics to improve public involvement and engagement (PIE) practices. By promoting [shared standards](#), resources and learning, PEDRI aims to strengthen the ways in which people and communities can shape and benefit from data-driven research.

[DARE UK \(Data and Analytics Research Environments UK\)](#) is a UK Research and Innovation programme that aims to establish a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments (TRES) where approved researchers can efficiently access and analyse sensitive data to advance research for public benefit. Together, PEDRI and DARE UK (also a founding member of PEDRI) play a central role in creating a trustworthy ecosystem for sensitive data research which takes public perspectives seriously and embeds transparency, accountability and effective PIE.

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes more prevalent across data research contexts, there is a growing need for shared understanding of how to involve the public meaningfully and consistently in decisions that affect them. Existing research shows that public awareness of AI in everyday applications is rising, but simply providing information, without creating opportunities for meaningful two-way engagement, does not guarantee public trust ([Ada Lovelace Institute, 2025](#); [UKRI, 2025](#)). There is also limited evidence exploring the public's understanding of how it is used in data research, for example, the use of sensitive data in training AI or machine learning (ML) models in TRES¹. Similarly, the public expect transparency and accountability when it comes to AI, yet the current PIE guidance does not fully address the specific challenges associated with AI in data research. This gap motivated the need for a roundtable to bring together expertise from across the data research and statistics community in order to surface challenges and begin a discussion on developing shared principles for effective PIE with AI in data research.

Background

As the use of AI accelerates across the data research landscape, effective PIE is essential. AI solutions are increasingly being used to help link, process and analyse large-scale data in ways that can enable significant societal value ([Ritchie et al, 2023](#)). Growing numbers of

¹Although AI/ML models within TRES are trained on de-identified data, they may still encode patterns that could indirectly reveal information about individuals. As models can be queried repeatedly and at scale, there remains a residual risk of re-identification.

requests to access TREs are seeking to use sensitive data to train AI models that can help draw conclusions from data more efficiently and accurately than humans. AI is helping improve healthcare pathways, better understand population-level trends and improve the efficiency of public services ([Tamilarasan et al, 2025](#)). Yet, AI technologies also raise questions about security, bias, and the balance between innovation and privacy ([Jefferson et al, 2022](#); [Ritchie et al, 2023](#); [Hotchkiss et al, 2024](#); [Ratti et al, 2025](#)).

Studies of technology governance highlight that trust is built not simply through technical performance, but through visible accountability to the public, including opportunities for public input and oversight ([Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, 2021](#); [Ada Lovelace Institute, 2025](#)). PIE provides a structured way to navigate the opportunities and challenges of AI in data research responsibly. It helps organisations understand what the public consider acceptable, their concerns, and their expectations from systems that use their data. By actively involving the public in decision-making about AI and use of data in training AI models, we can build trustworthy AI innovations and ensure alignment with societal values and public priorities.

Purpose of the roundtable

Against this backdrop, on 20 November 2025 PEDRI and DARE UK jointly hosted a collaborative roundtable to explore the challenges and opportunities for PIE with AI in data research. The event brought together 34 engagement specialists, researchers and members of the public to share learning and generate ideas for strengthening PIE in the area. To ground this discussion, the session included two presentations:

1. Dr Fatemeh Torabi (University of Cambridge & Dementias Platform UK) provided an introduction to AI in TREs.
2. Eleanor O’Keeffe (Ada Lovelace Institute) shared findings from recent work exploring public attitudes towards AI.

Their insights fed into discussions on:

- Cutting through hype and misconceptions about AI to have meaningful conversations about its role in data research.
- Priorities for PIE with AI and data research, including key questions for the public.
- Principles for effective PIE in a rapidly evolving field.

This report summarises the key themes identified during roundtable discussions. It serves as an initial step towards developing principles for effective PIE with AI and data research, and outlines suggested next steps for continuing this important conversation across the sector.

Key themes of the discussions

Inclusion, equity and representation

Discussions consistently reinforced that effective PIE with AI in data research must be inclusive, equitable and representative. The public is not a single, unified group; people hold different experiences, priorities and concerns shaped by their lived experiences. Treating the public as homogenous, such as assuming a population has the same concerns about AI or same expectations on how their data should be used, can risk reinforcing existing inequalities and creating a false sense of consensus.

A central message under this theme was the need to avoid tokenism. Rather than relying on the same voices or on a few people to represent the whole public, participants urged for intentional and tailored approaches to engage those who are often underrepresented in data research. Examples given included going into communities and hosting in-person activities in familiar local settings, rather than expecting people to come to organisations. Engagement activities should be tailored around the concerns, contexts and benefits specific to a particular community. In other words, answering the question “What’s in it for us?” and using examples that resonate with different communities. This can help to ensure that people see themselves reflected in conversations about data.

Equity was discussed not only in terms of PIE, but also in relation to data and AI itself. Participants made it clear that to ensure that AI models do not perpetuate or amplify bias, there is a requirement to include those from underserved communities in data used to train machine learning models. Inclusive PIE plays a dual role: it enriches the design and oversight of AI, and ensures the benefits are distributed fairly across society.

Effective public deliberation

From the discussions, it was clear that short meetings or webinars are insufficient when engaging the public in conversations about AI. To gain informed input from a diverse public audience, particularly on new and complex concepts such as this, it was stated that organisations must invest in sustained, large-scale public deliberation. Whilst project-level involvement activities can play a supportive role, they do not provide the depth or informed deliberative space needed for these conversations.

The quality of facilitation was identified as equally important. Conversations with the public must be open, non-leading, and supported by balanced information. It was observed that skilled facilitators are essential to ensure that the public feel comfortable to express disagreement, that quieter voices are included, and that discussions are not unintentionally steered towards a predetermined outcome. There should be space for disagreement and multiple perspectives, allowing people to express concerns and challenge ideas.

However, participants agreed that deliberative approaches will only lead to public trust if people can see how their input influences decisions. Outputs from deliberations need to be acted upon and meaningfully rolled out to the public, showing not only how specific projects use public insight, but also how policies and frameworks are shaped by it.

Data and AI literacy

A recurring theme from the roundtable was the importance of data and AI literacy to enable effective involvement and engagement. This was closely linked to inclusion, and the need to recognise that both professionals and the public have varying levels of existing knowledge and understanding about the role of AI in data research. Many people, including the public, policymakers, and frontline public-sector staff, may have limited familiarity with technical terms related to AI. Also, some may be unfamiliar with the distinction between publicly accessible AI tools, such as ChatGPT, from the training of AI models on sensitive data in TREs. Participants noted that consistent and accessible definitions, as well as specific use cases to demonstrate how AI is being used and developed in TREs, are essential to grounding engagement in shared understanding.

To make complex ideas more accessible, participants emphasised the value of creative PIE approaches. Visual and narrative formats, such as videos and cartoons, can help break down complex concepts and illustrate AI within the context of data research using real-life examples. Creative approaches can also support people to move beyond initial misconceptions and towards more informed opinions about AI in data research.

Shaping the narrative

Conversations about AI are currently dominated by sensational media headlines which can often generate fear or unrealistic expectations. As a result, it was highlighted that public perceptions about AI in the context of data research may also be shaped more by speculation than reality. It was felt that this is in part due to the absence of a coordinated presence in mainstream and social media from organisations working within the data

research ecosystem. There was a request from the group for stronger, more credible voices from the data research community to help anchor discussions with the public in evidence. This could be done by strengthening public communications beyond traditional PIE activities to raise general awareness, counter misinformation and help the public distinguish uses of AI with sensitive data in TREs.

Participants raised that effective communication also requires acknowledging societal anxieties directly, for example, job displacement, historical misuse of data, and unease about the rapid pace of technological change. By addressing these issues openly, rather than avoiding them, the sector can help to build legitimacy. This should include clear explanations of how AI models are developed using sensitive data and the safeguards in place, expressed in ways that resonate with the public. Positioning communications around public benefit was seen as particularly important amongst participants for helping the public understand the topic.

Trust and transparency

In discussions, participants stated that trust is not automatic; it must be earned. Transparency helps to create an environment where the public feel reassured, respected and able to be involved. Participants suggested that the public want clear and honest answers about how their data is used to develop and train AI models, as well as reassurance about who holds responsibility when AI gets it wrong. There was agreement that people are more likely to trust organisations that openly acknowledge the possibility of error and clearly explain the governance in place to prevent errors and the arrangements in place if something goes wrong.

Some participants felt that trust is closely linked to freedom of choice, and people should not feel coerced into sharing their data. Even when consent is not legally required for certain uses of data, clear communication about data use are essential to maintain trust. Clearly explaining the purpose and regulations surrounding use of sensitive data and AI can help to maintain user agency. Where consent is required, offering informed, non-coercive options to opt in or opt out ensures respect for individual choice.

Governance and clear accountability

Insights from the roundtable suggested that public confidence in the use of sensitive data to train AI models, as well as publicly accessible AI tools, hinges on robust governance that actively incorporates public perspectives from the outset. Concerns about safety, coercion,

and bias were raised as key public concerns, and these reflect genuine public priorities that must shape decision-making.

The group expressed that public input should be considered in the design of accountability mechanisms, including practical safeguards to ensure AI models are not operating outside of intended boundaries. These safeguards must be effective and communicated clearly to the public.

It was noted that regulation must be understandable and responsive to emerging risks. Participants argued that regulatory frameworks should demonstrate not only how harms will be addressed after they happen, but also how they are prevented through public-informed expectations and accountability mechanisms.

Data quality and standardisation

Discussions reflected a consensus that public concerns about inaccurate or biased AI models can be traced back to weaknesses in the underlying data used to train it, whether it be incomplete or inconsistent. Ensuring that data is high-quality, inclusive and standardised was identified as fundamental to trustworthy AI.

As the importance of data standardisation is often not understood by those who do not work with data, clear, accessible explanations are needed to show how better data leads to better outcomes for society. There was agreement that this could be done by demonstrating real-life examples of where improved data has reduced errors or service inequalities, highlighting data quality as a shared benefit rather than a technical detail.

Next steps: Collaboration and coordination

Reflecting on the roundtable discussion, next steps have been identified to advance conversations and strengthen PIE in the context of AI in data research. There is currently a great deal of activity in the broader field of public attitudes towards AI. In this dynamic landscape, PEDRI plays a crucial role in coordinating these efforts in the data research context specifically, helping to connect stakeholders, share learning, and avoid duplication. By providing this coordination, PEDRI can ensure that progress in engaging the public with AI is efficient, coherent, and builds on existing expertise, ultimately fostering more effective and trusted engagement with the public. A starting point for this will be to define a set of principles to guide these PIE efforts which participants began to discuss at the roundtable.

Data research organisations should collaborate on large-scale public deliberations to engage diverse members of the public in conversations about the use of sensitive data to train AI models within TREs. To this end, DARE UK will be leading a UK-wide public dialogue in 2026 to explore views on the topic with communities across the nation. The goal is to produce initial guidance for data custodians, researchers and others training or using AI with sensitive data to do so in a way that meets public expectations. Other organisations in the sector are encouraged to partner and collaborate with DARE UK, ensuring alignment, sharing learning, and avoiding duplication of effort to enable maximum reach and impact.

Conclusion

The roundtable made it clear that involving and engaging the public in conversations about the training and development of AI models in data research is not optional; it is essential for demonstrating trustworthiness. Importantly, the discussions surface several sector-wide gaps. These gaps are prioritising inclusion and equity as foundational principles, the growing urgency for sustained, large-scale public deliberation, and the absence of coordinated, evidence-based communication to counter misinformation. There was also shared recognition that PIE must extend beyond project-level decisions, such as in shaping governance expectations and accountability mechanisms.

These collective insights point to a clearer agenda for the sector. Moving forward, collaboration and coordination will be critical to amplify impact, avoid duplication and create a coherent approach that reflects public priorities. PEDRI and DARE UK are well-positioned to lead this effort, helping to translate these insights into practical guidance and activities to ensure that PIE is not an afterthought, but a core component of responsible AI.

Appendix: Participants

The roundtable brought together representatives from across data research, statistics and public engagement and the public.

Participating organisations, teams and individuals	Number of representatives
Ada Lovelace Institute	1
ADR UK (Administrative Research UK)	2
BHF DSC (British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre), including one public representative	2
Cancer Research UK	1
DARE UK	1
DARE UK Public Advisory Group	8
HDR UK Federated Analytics Programme	1
Health Innovation East	1
Health Innovation KSS (Kent, Surrey, Sussex)	1
PEDRI	2
Health Innovation North East and North Cumbria, including one public representative	2
Research Data Scotland	1
Scottish AI Alliance	1
Scottish Government	1
TREvolution, including two public co-leads	3
UK LLC (UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration)	1
University of Cambridge	1
University of Bristol	1
Understanding Patient Data	1
Yorkshire and Humber Secure Data Environment	2